

PROGRAMS OF TEACHING WOMEN TO TEXTILE CRAFT IN KARAKALPAK FOLK PEDAGOGY

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Annotation: In this article, information is provided about the programs of teaching women to textile craft in Karakalpak folk pedagogy. In addition, the history of making the garment, which is considered the national dress of Karakalpak women, its patterns and the researches of scientists are analyzed.

We have a priceless heritage of our people that has arrived from the thousand-year past, which reflects their way of life. Some of them are being continued by the present generations. One of these traditions is the weaving craft of our women. Weaving is the main type of work that our women have been engaged in since early, and it prepares our daughters for the next marriage, in marriage. is of great importance in acquiring one's profession. In the people of Karakalpak, after the girl reaches the age of seven, she takes a needle in her hand and sews things that she will not need in the future, and collects them in a chest. When the time came, when the girl was old enough to get married, he found out about her interest in the craft and her hard work by looking at the sewing and sewing work she did before the wedding. , the interior of which is decorated with the girl's hand-made embroideries. It had everything the family needed, and the newlyweds lived together in it. The crafts of girls include weaving, tailoring, carpet and embroidery, quilt making and similar crafts. Weaving has its own difficulties and requires a lot of patience in a woman's work. Even so, some of the embroidered pieces of clothing, the composition and colors of which are created in our nation, are not found in any of the peoples of Central Asia.

Dresses that women can wear on marriages and weddings, jewelry used on holidays. Pictures were created showing the love and affection of our daughters. Among them are beautiful dresses, beautiful dresses, red dresses, sleeveless dresses, string dresses, and other clothes of the Soukeli people. In the 19th century and in the 20th century, red clothes were more common. It resembles the clothes of the groom, the bride, the virgin.. Published in 1902 in the Russian newspaper A .. Song. Rossikova's article describes the red shirt of the Karakalpak people. † Wore gloves to put on clothes at all prestigious gatherings. Each corner of the body was made of four corners, and it resembled a human face. All the empty spaces were covered with red thread. If you look at Asian carpets, you can find many similarities in the patterns of the khaki carpet.

In the 30s of the 20th century, special attention was paid to vocational training and art classes in newly opened schools. For this purpose, the sewing art of the Karakalpak people, which was created for the purpose of educating girls, is important as valuable materials that have preserved the original historical signs, and here it has a strong connection with the ethnic history and ethnogenesis of the Karakalpak people, as well as their worldview. It is important in the history of training girls to trade.

With this in mind, it is also called folklore. the world-famous thoughts of the people are expressed.. In the mobile initiative, a person becomes skilled in imagining the infinite view of the nature that lives around him, the universe. . Models of elements surrounded by ramparts are the best way to create. These are the information given to them by the nomadic peoples, they help to understand the folk stories about the creation of the world and religious ceremonies. taught to decorate with artistic glasses with software marks Pictorial patterns, which have become a distinctive form of visual art, have marked the ideas that

have been established in the social life of people, and have marked them in the form of ring-shaped symbols associated with religious inspirations. encourages to know their ancestors and national traditions. Also, they used to tie clothes and shelter over themselves to protect themselves from spirits.. '# 91; It was registered by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 5, 2005. Depicting symbols and signs, drawings filled a world of interconnected images. # 91; It was registered by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 5, 2005. In studying the decorative patterns taught by the Karakalpaks to their daughters, the Karakalpak software can provide the most important and acceptable information. A self-closing dressing appears diamond-shaped. This form is from the late Eneolithic period, and the harvester is a symbol of multiple parentage. Our ancestors were tempted to have a son, but Eve did not tempt her. The presence of a diamond-shaped copy of the symbol indicates that it was preserved in the Air view [2;6,8]. She is wearing a dress with stripes on her chest, a red ribbon around her neck, and a wedding headdress. Exhibition made of white, blue, yellow, dark colored yarn, made in the form of a rhombus. The original idea of the rhombus sign was carried out in a triangular shape on the wall. Three parts of one of them looked to the sky, which was a divine symbol, which means that the man is the head of the world. It gives the meaning.. Since the man and the dream, the sky and the earth have collided with each other, the two worlds that have collided will come true. Even though the wedding dresses are triangular in shape, their essence is the same, but they have a rhombus shape.

Researcher Irina Bogoslovskaya's study of hundreds of kymeshek and its components from private collections in many countries of the world, especially the front of kymeshek, gave her the opportunity to determine the casting characteristics of the patterns. Twelve types of basic motifs are used in the central black border of the front of the kyzyl kymeshek . Each of these patterns is considered a unique symbol of Karakalpak society and tribes. The reason is that there are 12 tribes of Karakalpaks like 12 patterns; kiyat, ashamayl, koldavly, kastamgali, balgali, kandekli, karamoyin, müyten, kitay, kipshaq, keneges, mangît. Karakalpak originated in embroidery patterns [3;48].

The patterns on the dresses served as a symbol to mean their daughters which tribe they belong to on their wedding day. It is known that more than 100 Karakalpak weddings were held based on traditions specific to one or another tribe. For this reason, at the wedding ceremony, the bride's dress must be marked with the symbols of her tribe and society, such as embroidered patterns.

Scholar I. Bogoslovsky described that 12 main types of patterns were given to the edge of the long sleeves located in the middle of the front side of the Karakalpak wedding dresses. Scientist A. Allamuratov, commenting on Karakalpaks' teaching of embroidery to their daughters, distinguished 4 main types of the long-sleeved fringe located in the middle of the front of the Kyzyl kymeshek. By this, he meant the compositional solution of the pattern line in the middle of the shirt. Scientist I. Bogoslovsky believed that it would be correct if the long-sleeved fringe in the middle of the front of Karakalpak's kyzyl kymeshek divided the black patterns into twelve. The reason is that this dress has twelve different patterns. Many people have confirmed in their scientific studies that the symbols of different societies and tribes are marked in the mentioned patterns.

According to The famous scientist I.V. Savickiyd, sewing diamond-shaped patterns on shirts is especially common among the MUYTEN tribe of Karakalpaks[3;49]. It is possible to say that this cotton also belonged to the MUYTEN tribe of Karakalpaks with two large flower patterns. The interesting thing is that the patterns on the front of the Kyzyl Kiyemeshek look like a tree of life, based on a certain pattern. It is three-dimensional from top to the vertical; which means the birth, development and end of life. In the patterns on the lower part of the garment, there are objects related to the underworld; Although frogs, snakes, scorpions, and spiders are depicted, water, zoomorphs, plant motifs and symbols related to life on earth are shown more. This form is considered a symbol of aspiration to heaven. The black fringe of the sleeve sewn to the center of the front of the shirt represents the distance between heaven and earth. From the appearance of the patterns on the edge of it, it looked like an ancient cradle of Karakalpak. Although the patterns on the black border of the center front of the shirt are different, the pattern they have is reminiscent of a crib shape. The sky is blue and the color blue in Karakalpaks is considered to be a woman's tolerance.

Perhaps this person assumed that it could be a sign of the fallen tree in the sky. A certain theory of the connection between the earth and the sky. Wide black cords wrapped around the middle of the front of the dress indicate the bride's tribe. Patterns with a sharp shape will be a symbol of the future world. The stripes in the center of the fabric worn on the red dress are depicted in a symbol that indicates the social level of the imagination. The analysis of the style of patterned tables in Karakalpak art shows that all patterns given in the form of birds, animals, plants, and geometric shapes have fulfilled their function. All of them have a great impact, contain a unique image of their objects and represent the traditions of the people, which were realized in a long historical process, entering the world

Decorative patterns are the images and symbols that realize people's thoughts about studying nature, their worldview related to diligence, their aesthetic desires, and the close connection of needlework to the imagination and knowledge of the world. indicates that.

Thus, if we want to study the cultural and educational history of the Karakalpak people, we will understand that our nation has a rich educational heritage and wonderful arts. Also, in educating the younger generation, they enjoy our cultural heritage, instill in women an interest in the art of weaving and become one of the most important teachers today.

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